

NONDESTRUCTIVE EVALUATION OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS
USING A RAMAN OPTOMECHANICAL STRAIN GAUGE

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ABSTRACT

An optomechanical strain gauge has been developed which can be used to study the internal strain in composite specimens. To illustrate the technique model composites have been prepared consisting of a polydiacetylene fibre in an epoxy resin matrix. In some specimens the matrix was reinforced by glass fibres while in other specimens blunt cracks were cut into the edge of the matrix. Uniaxial stress was applied to the specimens and the strain at all points along the polydiacetylene fibre measured using Raman spectroscopy. The critical length of the fibres could be measured directly; in unreinforced specimens this length was in good agreement with the predictions of shear-lag theories. In the glass reinforced specimens the critical length decreased with increasing fibre volume fraction. In the cracked specimens it was possible to observe considerable strain multiplication ahead of the crack tip.

INTRODUCTION

There are a variety of nondestructive techniques which have been used to study the reaction of fibre composites to stress [1]. One limitation which most share is an inability to measure directly the stress or strain in the reinforcing fibres. Recently we have developed a technique which achieves that capability for composites in which the matrix is transparent and the reinforcing fibres are crystalline polymers. This optomechanical technique uses the crystalline polymer fibre as the sensor and a laser-Raman spectrometer as a remote detector.

The vibrational frequencies of a polymer are determined by the atomic masses and interatomic force constants along

the polymer backbone. When the backbone is stretched the increased interatomic separation leads to a decrease in the force constants and hence in the vibrational frequencies. Using Raman spectroscopy we have demonstrated this property for crystalline fibres of polydiacetylenes and Kevlar [2,3]. Polydiacetylenes have the backbone structure $(=RC-C\equiv C-CR=)_n$ and have been synthesised with a large number of different sidegroups, R. Figure 1 illustrates the decrease in the frequency of the Raman band associated with vibration of the triple bond for a polydiacetylene single crystal fibre subjected to axial strain. Using this and similar figures for calibration, polydiacetylene fibres included in composites can be used as internal strain gauges [4].

In the present paper we report on three examples of the application of the optomechanical strain gauge to composites. Raman spectroscopy was first used to measure the point-to-point variation of the fibre strain in a model system consisting of a single polydiacetylene fibre in an epoxy resin matrix. In the second example the strain distribution along polydiacetylene fibres included in glass fibre/epoxy composites was measured. Finally we have investigated the strain distribution in polydiacetylene fibres located near crack tips in epoxy resin specimens.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Polydiacetylene fibres were prepared by first growing needle-like crystals of the substituted diacetylene monomer derivative, 1,6-di-(N-carbazolyl)-2,4-hexadiyne (DCHD)[5]. Selected DCHD crystals were polymerised by exposure to 35 to 40 Mrad of ^{60}Co γ -radiation. The polymer chains (polyDCHD) form parallel to the long axis of the needle-like crystals as a result of the topochemical reaction, thus creating single-crystal polymer fibres [6]. The fibres have a Young's modulus of 45 ± 1 GPa in the axial direction.

Composite samples were prepared using Ciba-Geigy XD927 two-part solvent-free cold-setting epoxy resin, using 100 parts by weight of resin to 36 parts of hardener. The Young's modulus of this matrix material was found to be 2.8 ± 0.1 GPa. Figure 2 illustrates a single fibre specimen with the polyDCHD fibre located in the centre of the epoxy resin matrix. A thin film resistance strain gauge can be seen attached to the surface of the specimen at the centre of the fibre. Blunt cracks were created in some specimens by making saw cuts from the edge towards the centre of the fibre. Chopped-strand glass fibres of 12 μm diameter and approximately 15 mm long were added to some specimens. The glass fibres were aligned parallel to the specimen axis; the volume fraction of the fibres in the composite was less than 10 %.

A small tensile loading device was used to apply stress in the fibre direction. The device was mounted on a micrometer slide so that the whole length of the specimen could be traversed through the incident laser beam. Spatial resolution at the specimen was approximately equal to the 25

Figure 1. Raman frequency of the triple bond vibration of a polydiacetylene (polyDCHD) single crystal fibre as a function of elastic strain in the chain direction.

Figure 2. Photograph of an epoxy specimen containing a polyDCHD fibre with a resistance strain gauge attached.

μm diameter of the focal spot of the 2 mW laser beam (638 or 676 nm) used to excite the Raman spectra. As shown in Figure 1 the 2085 cm^{-1} Raman line of polyDCHD fibres shifts to lower frequency by $19.7 \pm 0.4\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for a 1 % increase in uniaxial strain. Since the position of the Raman line can be typically measured to $\pm 2\text{ cm}^{-1}$ then the strain in the fibre can be measured to an absolute accuracy of $\pm 0.1\%$. Changes in the strain can be measured with greater precision.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The distribution of strain along a single polyDCHD fibre is shown in Figure 3 for three different levels of applied matrix strain. It can be seen that when the matrix is deformed the strain starts from a finite value at the end of the fibre and increases towards the centre. The saturation value for the fibre strain, approximately equal to the matrix strain, is reached in a distance equal to half the "critical length". This critical length is not the same as that determined by fibre pull-out tests which is a function only of the fibre and interfacial shear strengths and does not correspond to the actual bonding conditions in a composite [7]. The strain distribution shown in Figure 3 is qualitatively similar to that first predicted by the shear-lag model of Cox [8]. The predictions of more detailed calculations using finite difference techniques are in quantitative agreement with the results [9]. Both theoretical approaches suggest that the ratio of the critical length to the fibre diameter depends primarily upon the ratio of the fibre modulus to the matrix modulus. This prediction has been verified by the authors experimentally [4].

Figure 4 shows the strain distribution along a polydiacetylene fibre which was located near the end of a manufactured blunt crack in an epoxy specimen. The 0.8 mm wide crack was cut perpendicular to the polyDCHD fibre to a depth of 2.8 mm through the 7.3 mm wide specimen. The blunt end of the crack was 0.6 mm away from the $95\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ diameter fibre. The presence of the crack in the specimen increased the strain in the fibre by approximately a factor of 3.5. Photoelastic studies confirmed that the strain measured in the matrix was similar to that experienced by the fibre in the vicinity of the crack. A theoretical description of the stress field about cracks in two-dimensional semi-infinite plates has been given by Williams [10]. Using parameters appropriate to the present geometry this model predicts a stress multiplication factor of 3.4, in good agreement with the experimental measurement.

The strain at the centre of the polyDCHD fibre in another specimen with a blunt crack is plotted against matrix strain in Figure 5. The open points show the data recorded during loading, the filled points during unloading. The discontinuities in strain occurred at points where the strain distribution studies were made and show that the epoxy matrix was yielding. This process led to a permanent strain in the fibre when the stress applied to the matrix was

Figure 3. Axial strain as a function of position along the fibre at various matrix strains.

Figure 4. Axial strain as a function of position along the fibre at various matrix strains for a specimen with a blunt crack. The relative position of the crack is indicated.

Figure 5. Strain at the midpoint of polyDCHD fibre as a function of the strain in the epoxy matrix in which it was included. The fibre was located near the tip of a manufactured crack in the epoxy specimen.

Figure 6. Axial strain in a polyDCHD fibre included in an epoxy-based composite specimen containing 8.3 % by volume glass fibres. The dashed line is the strain expected in an unreinforced specimen.

released.

The effect of stiffening of the matrix by the inclusion of glass fibres can be seen in Figure 6. This figure shows the strain distribution in the vicinity of the end of a polyDCHD fibre incorporated in a epoxy resin matrix containing 8.3 % by volume of glass fibres. Also plotted in the figure is a dashed line which represents the strain distribution which would have been expected for a polyDCHD fibre in an unreinforced matrix. The critical length has been reduced and the strain at the fibre end increased by the addition of the glass fibres. Application of the rule of mixtures equation predicted that the effective modulus of the composite material in which the polyDCHD fibre was embedded had been increased from 2.8 GPa to 5.0 GPa. The change in the critical length shown in Figure 6 is approximately equal to that expected from the estimated change in matrix modulus. Detailed comparisons are not justified at this stage since the distribution of glass fibres in the specimen was inhomogeneous. It is clear, however, that in a particular fibre/matrix combination there is not a unique critical length. This length of fibre which is necessary to build up to maximum stress is dependent upon the volume fraction of the fibres in the composite as well as the ratio of the elastic moduli.

CONCLUSIONS

The Raman optomechanical strain gauge shows considerable promise as a tool for the nondestructive evaluation of composites. Most conventional techniques lack the capability it has to measure in situ deformations. Examples have been given of the determination of the critical length of a reinforcing fibre and the reduction of that length with increasing volume fraction of fibres in the composite. Quantitative measurement of the stress multiplication at a crack tip has also been demonstrated.

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